

The Role of Values in the Psychological Well-Being of Residents Across Different Regions of Russia

Victoria N. Galyapina¹, Zarina H. Lepshokova¹, Ivan A. Apollonov²

¹ National Research University Higher School of Economics, Moscow, 101000, Russia

² Kuban State Technological University, Krasnodar, 350072, Russia

Received 14 February 2024 ♦ Accepted 15 July 2024 ♦ Published 11 March 2025

Citation: Galyapina VN, Lepshokova ZH, Apollonov IA (2025) The Role of Values in the Psychological Well-Being of Residents Across Different Regions of Russia. *Population and Economics* 9(1):25-44. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.9.e120895>

Abstract

This article is devoted to studying an important issue for any society – the identification of values that influence people’s psychological well-being. The authors focus on a cross-regional comparison, as previous studies have highlighted the role of regional context in shaping both the expression of values and the psychological well-being of regional populations. This suggests that there are both universal and region-specific patterns in the relationship between values and psychological well-being among residents of different regions of Russia.

The study sample consisted of ethnic Russians from two Russian regions – Moscow region (N = 318) and Krasnodar Krai (N = 407). We analyzed the expression of ten values and indicators of psychological well-being (self-esteem and life satisfaction), controlling for respondents’ age, gender, education, and income. ANOVA and hierarchical regression were used for data analysis.

The results indicate that Russians in Krasnodar Krai have significantly higher psychological well-being than those in Moscow region. This may be due to the region’s climatic characteristics and its well-developed recreational industry. Compared to residents of Moscow region, Russians in Krasnodar Krai place greater importance on the values of Stimulation, Hedonism, Achievement, and Benevolence, while those in Moscow region exhibit stronger values of Self-direction, Security, and Conformity. These differences are statistically significant. The values of Power, Tradition, and Universalism do not show significant regional differences.

A universal pattern found in both regions is the positive relationship between Self-direction and self-esteem, as well as between Tradition and life satisfaction. However, certain value-psychological well-being relationships appear to be region-specific: in Moscow region, Benevolence and Conformity positively associate with psychological well-being, whereas in Krasnodar Krai, Universalism, Security, and Achievement show a positive relationship with well-being.

In the context of the complex modern situation, where there is a perceived threat to the country, values associated with self-protection and anxiety avoidance – Tradition, Conformity, and Security – are found to predict psychological well-being among Russians across regions. The study’s findings highlight the importance of considering regional specificities when examining the value foundations of psychological well-being.

Keywords

values, psychological well-being, Moscow region, Krasnodar Krai, Russia

JEL codes: I31; R58

Introduction

Caring for the well-being of a country’s inhabitants is a key priority for any state. Well-being is most often analyzed through fundamental socio-economic indicators, such as per capita income, or by evaluating the outcomes of socio-economic development, including human capital quality, which takes into account education, health, and other factors (Malkina 2016).

However, beyond material and social well-being, psychological well-being is also a crucial component of domestic policy. Researchers from various disciplines, including psychology, sociology, and political science, examine psychological well-being and its determinants, as it is significant not only for individuals but also for society as a whole. An increase in subjective psychological well-being serves as an important measure of the positive impact of social policies (Lyubomirsky et al. 2005).

Psychological well-being research

Subjective psychological well-being is a broad concept that encompasses individuals’ emotional reactions, satisfaction across various life domains, and overall judgments about life satisfaction (Diener et al. 1998). It is not a singular construct but rather a combination of multiple interrelated components (Stones and Kozma 1985). Life satisfaction is often considered the cognitive component of subjective well-being (Diener et al. 1998). Meanwhile, self-satisfaction or self-esteem is typically viewed as an emotional and evaluative component, reflecting a positive or negative attitude toward oneself (Rosenberg 1965) and a subjective assessment of one’s personal worth (Orth and Robins 2014). In Carol Ryff’s model (1989), subjective psychological well-being is understood as an individual’s self-esteem and perception of their own life, as well as a measure of positive psychological functioning.

Russian researchers emphasize the inherently subjective nature of well-being and argue that the term “subjective” is unnecessary when discussing psychological well-being (Kulikov 2000; Shamionov 2010). Studies suggest that psychological well-being reflects a person’s self-perception, attitude toward life, and personal experiences of satisfaction. Furthermore, the significance of these experiences is shaped by internalized normative concepts of a “prosperous” external and internal environment (Shamionov 2010). These perceptions are largely influenced by socialization processes, particularly socio-cultural conditions. The role of cultural context in psychological well-being has also been highlighted in research by S. Nartova-Bochaver (2005).

A cross-cultural study conducted among young people in China, Italy, Russia, and the United States examined the relationship between psychological well-being and cultural dimensions such as vertical and horizontal collectivism and individualism (Germani et al. 2021). The findings revealed that, at the cultural level, the higher a country's individualism index, the higher its average life satisfaction score. At the individual level, life satisfaction was not associated with horizontal or vertical individualism but showed a positive correlation with vertical collectivism. According to the authors, this highlights the significant role of family ties in life satisfaction across different cultures during the transition to adulthood.

Thus, both domestic and international researchers emphasize cognitive and emotional components when studying psychological well-being, as these components serve as key measures of human and societal quality of life. In this context, it is essential to understand the factors that underpin psychological well-being. This study focuses on personality values as a key psychological factor.

Values and psychological well-being

Researchers have noted that individual values, as guiding principles in a person's life, shape decisions and attitudes (Bilsky and Schwartz 1994; Sagiv and Schwartz 2000) and can influence psychological well-being (Schwartz 1992). Bilsky V. and Schwartz S. (1994) argue that certain values are rooted in the need for growth and development – such as Stimulation, Self-direction, Universalism, and Benevolence – while others are based on scarce needs, including Conformity, Tradition, Security, and Power. Achievement values belong to both categories (Schwartz 2012a). According to the authors, the former contribute to psychological well-being, whereas the latter do not.

A meta-analysis of data from 32 countries (Sortheix and Schwartz 2017) empirically confirmed that values associated with Openness to change (which emphasize growth and personal focus) positively correlate with psychological well-being, whereas values linked to Conservation (avoidance of anxiety and social focus) show a negative correlation. Additionally, results from a longitudinal study based on 12 waves of public surveys in Germany (N = 9,723) demonstrated a positive relationship between psychological well-being and values related to Openness to change (Grosz et al. 2021).

It has also been found that culture moderates the relationship between values and psychological well-being (Sortheix and Schwartz 2017). Specifically, a low level of cultural egalitarianism strengthens the positive relationship between values of Openness to change and well-being, as well as the positive relationship between values of Self-Enhancement and well-being. At the same time, it amplifies the negative relationships between values of Conservation and well-being, as well as between values of Self-Transcendence and well-being.

However, some studies have shown that values promoting self-affirmation and personal interests can, in fact, reduce psychological well-being (Sagiv and Schwartz 2000; Bojanowska and Czerw 2020; Bobowik et al. 2011).

A cross-cultural study conducted in Russia among Russian and Kazakh students (Shamionov 2014) using the *Cultural and Value Differential method* revealed distinct value predictors of psychological well-being in these groups. Among Kazakh students, “respect for authority” was a positive predictor of well-being, whereas among Russian students, “cordiality” was found to be a negative predictor.

It is evident that values serve as predictors of psychological well-being. However, the nature of their effect – whether positive or negative – varies across studies conducted on in-

dividuals from different ethnocultural groups. In our view, examining the socio-cultural context of respondents' regions of residence can help clarify the contradictory role of values in psychological well-being.

Regionalism in the study of values

Interest in regional studies remains high. Researchers employ various approaches to studying regions, including geographical approaches (based on physical and geographical criteria), civilizational approaches (based on cultural and demographic characteristics), as well as constructivist and postmodern perspectives. The latter view regions as analytical constructs shaped by the researcher's perception, which may "overlap" with objective reality for the purposes of systematization and typologization (Efremova 2017). Until the early 21st century, regionalism was largely seen as the opposite of globalism. However, in contemporary discourse, globalization and regionalization are increasingly understood as interdependent processes. Moreover, regionalization is now considered an integral part of global developments, leading to the emergence of a distinct field known as comparative regionalism (Acharya 2012; Laursen 2003). In Russia, the issues of interregionalism and transregionalism have been explored by scholars such as D.A. Kuznetsov (Kuznetsov 2016), M.L. Lagutina, and others (Lagutina and Mikhailenko 2020).

In studies on cross-country and intra-country value comparisons, Fischer and Schwartz (2011) demonstrate that value consistency and consensus within a single country tend to be lower than those observed between countries. The authors attribute intra-country differences to the complexity of regional and social structures, which weakens value coherence. They also note that while national consensus on values may be limited, agreement is more likely for values of medium and low importance. Schwartz and Fischer support their conclusions with data from a sample of 67 countries. They argue that social institutions and other macro-level variables shape the importance of values, but individuals internalize these values to varying degrees. As a result, regional, professional, and other demographic groups prioritize different values based on their unique experiences and interests, leading to a lower overall level of value consensus within a country.

Furthermore, Fischer and Schwartz (2011) identify a subset of values whose significance is strongly influenced by cultural factors. Values such as respect for parents and success, for instance, tend to exhibit a relatively high degree of national consensus. This suggests that the level of value agreement within a country varies considerably depending on the specific values in question.

The idea of regional differences in values within the same country is also supported by the research of Magun and Rudnev (2010). Their study on Ukraine revealed regional variations in value importance: residents of Western Ukraine exhibited stronger conservative values compared to those in the central and eastern regions of the country.

A study conducted in the Central Federal District among the Russian ethnic minority and titular ethnic groups revealed significant differences in value preferences. The values of ethnic Russians differed markedly from those of the titular ethnic groups in two republics of the North Caucasus Federal District, as well as from those of ethnic Russians residing in these regions. Specifically, Russians in the Central Federal District exhibited a stronger preference for individually oriented values. Additionally, Russians in the two Caucasian republics demonstrated a higher degree of value alignment with the titular ethnic groups than with ethnic Russians from the Central Federal District. Researchers attribute these

differences to the influence of modernization processes in the studied regions (Galyapina et al. 2018).

The role of modernization in shaping value preferences has also been explored by both foreign (Schwartz 2012; Inglehart and Welzel 2003) and domestic (Leonidova et al. 2017) scholars. According to modernization theory, modernization is linked to the transition toward modern societies, characterized by the adoption of Western social institutions and value systems.

Beyond cross-regional studies, research focusing on specific regions provides further insights. Of particular relevance to this study are the findings of Vnukova L.B. (2020), who analyzed the values of youth in Southern Russia. Her research indicates that respondents predominantly prioritize individual values, such as freedom of movement, personal security, and independence in thought and action. At the same time, many participants also value socially oriented principles, including tolerance, the right to choose their government, social justice, and equality. These findings suggest that both individually focused values – such as freedom and independence – and socially oriented values – such as tolerance and security – hold significant importance for young people in Southern Russia.

A study on the value orientations of Muscovites revealed that freedom is prioritized as a key life value (Arutyunova 2014). Furthermore, research by Z. Lepshokova and M. Vylegzhanina (2017) found that native Russian Muscovites place the highest importance on the values associated with Openness to change, followed by values of Self-Transcendence, Conservation, and lastly, Self-Enhancement. This suggests that for Russians in the Moscow region, values with a personal focus – such as independence and freedom – are of primary importance, and they are closely linked to openness to new experiences.

Regionalism in psychological well-being research

In Russia, there is a considerable body of interregional research on well-being, although much of it focuses on material or social well-being (Malkina 2016, 2017; Korobitsyn 2015; Pyzhev and Pyzheva, 2015). However, there have been attempts to analyze psychological well-being indicators across different regions, such as feelings of cheerfulness, good mood, calmness, relaxation, activity, and energy. According to Rosstat data for 2021 (The regions of Russia with the most psychologically healthy inhabitants are named ... 2021), the most psychologically well-off men are in the Republic of Tuva (88.8%), the Jewish Autonomous Region (87.5%), and Kalmykia (86.8%), while the highest proportion of psychologically healthy women are in the Republic of Tuva (85.3%), Yakutia (81.7%), and Ingushetia (80.6%). The regions with the lowest proportion of psychologically healthy males are Karachay-Cherkessia (56.5%), Adygea (60.1%), and Tambov Oblast (60.6%), while for females, the lowest proportions are found in Tambov Oblast (44.9%), Khakassia (47.8%), and Novgorod Oblast (48.7%). In Moscow, 67.5% of men and 59% of women are psychologically healthy.

Researchers employ various approaches to explain regional and national differences in well-being. Some studies attribute disparities in psychological well-being to macroeconomic indicators such as GDP and average income levels, with research showing that these factors are correlated with public assessments of well-being (Salnikova 2019). Other studies emphasize the importance of climatic characteristics and recreational opportunities in influencing well-being. A study by Kovalev S.Y. et al. (2017) demonstrated that climate significantly affects Russians' subjective well-being assessments, placing it on par with other factors commonly analyzed, such as income, employment, health status, and environmental

quality (e.g., drinking water and air quality). Additionally, a study by Apatova and Avdeeva (2016) examined the recreational infrastructure of Russian regions, showing that it contributes to the complex socio-economic development of the region and plays a role in improving the health and overall well-being of its inhabitants.

Research in Russia has focused on examining values and well-being across different regions. In explaining interregional differences in psychological well-being, researchers have relied on both macroeconomic indicators and the climatic and recreational characteristics of the regions. When studying regional value differences, the level of modernization or traditionalism has often been a key consideration. Studies have shown that in more modernized regions, such as Moscow region, personal values associated with Openness to change and novelty are more pronounced. In contrast, in more traditional regions, such as the republics of the North Caucasus, values with a social focus, such as Conservation and Self-Transcendence, are more prominent. In the Southern regions of Russia, both personal and social-focused values are of significant importance to residents.

Among the comprehensive studies examining the relationship between collectivism/individualism and well-being in Russian regions, a notable example is the work of M. Minkov and colleagues (Minkov et al. 2023). The authors found that the relationship between cultural orientations and well-being varies regionally and is influenced by factors such as regional well-being and geographical location, which are relevant to business development, including investment levels and the quality of management. However, their study did not specifically address psychological well-being or the role of specific values. The present study aims to fill this gap by conducting a cross-regional analysis to identify both universal and region-specific patterns of values and psychological well-being in Moscow region and Krasnodar Krai.

Socio-cultural context of Moscow region and Krasnodar Krai

The socio-cultural contexts of Moscow region (comprising Moscow and Moscow Oblast) and Krasnodar Krai present both similarities and distinct differences.

Firstly, these are some of the most populous regions in Russia: Moscow ranks first with a population of 13,104,177 people, Moscow Oblast is second with 8,591,736 people, and Krasnodar Krai ranks third with 5,819,345 people (Population of the regions... 2023).

Secondly, both Moscow region and Krasnodar Krai are among the top ten regions in terms of socio-economic development: Moscow holds the first place, Moscow Oblast is fourth, and Krasnodar Krai ranks eighth. These regions are also competitive, with Moscow at the top, Moscow Oblast in third, and Krasnodar Krai in seventh place. In terms of quality of life and investment climate, the regions remain in the top five: Moscow – 1st place, Moscow Oblast – 3rd place, Krasnodar Krai – 5th place, according to 2022 data (Batchaev 2022).

Thirdly, these regions are highly attractive to both internal and external migrants. Between 2019 and 2021, migration growth in Moscow Oblast amounted to 274.43 thousand people, the highest in the Russian Federation. Krasnodar Krai followed with 112.24 thousand people, and Moscow had 71.98 thousand people migrating during the same period (Batchaev 2022). Notably, Krasnodar Krai is currently hosting a significant number of forced migrants from Ukraine and new territories of the Russian Federation.

Fourth, Russians form the numerical majority in both Moscow region and Krasnodar Krai (National composition of Russian regions 2023). However, both regions are also culturally diverse: in Moscow Oblast, 92.9% of the population are Russians, followed by Ukraini-

ans (1.79%), Armenians (0.95%), Tatars (0.84%), Belarusians (0.47%), and Uzbeks (0.39%); in Moscow, Russians make up 91.65%, Ukrainians (1.42%), Tatars (1.38%), Armenians (0.98%), and Azerbaijanis (0.53%); in Krasnodar Krai, Russians constitute 88.3%, Armenians (5.5%), Ukrainians (1.6%), and Tatars (0.5%).

However, the nature of multiculturalism in these regions differs. In Moscow region, multiculturalism is predominantly a result of recent migration processes. In contrast, Krasnodar Krai's multiculturalism has historical roots, as indigenous Adyge peoples and various other ethnic groups, such as Armenians, Greeks, Germans, Moldovans, and Estonians, have lived in the region for generations. This long-term residence has led to the "indigenization" of these ethnic groups (Baranov and Skorobogatov 2019). Another distinctive feature of Krasnodar Krai is the presence of a sub-ethnic group of Cossacks, whose history of migration has significantly shaped the region's ethnosocial relations (Mukha 2012). Furthermore, the region's geographical location, bordering national republics such as Adygea, adds to its multicultural complexity.

Another key difference is the level of urbanization. According to Rosstat, approximately 45.1% of the population in Krasnodar Krai lives in rural areas (Krasnodar Krai in figures 2021). In contrast, Moscow has one of the highest urbanization rates, with 98.3% of the population residing in cities, and Moscow Oblast has 78.5% urban dwellers (The level of urbanization of the regions ... 2022). This highlights the more rural character of Krasnodar Krai compared to the highly urbanized Moscow region.

The regions also differ significantly in their climatic conditions, which influence their economic characteristics. In Krasnodar Krai, agriculture and tourism are prominent, whereas industrial production plays a more significant role in Moscow and Moscow region. Despite these differences, both Krasnodar Krai and Moscow region are recognized as key recreational destinations in Russia. According to the National Tourism Rating for 2024, Moscow and Moscow Oblast occupy the 1st and 2nd positions, respectively, while Krasnodar Krai ranks 3rd in terms of tourist attractiveness (National Tourism Rating 2024). This indicates that the primary distinctions between the regions lie in their climatic and economic conditions.

Another notable difference is the development patterns within each region. Moscow and Moscow Oblast are more heterogeneous in terms of development, with significant disparities between urban and rural areas. In contrast, Krasnodar Krai exhibits greater consistency in the development of its territories. Moreover, Moscow and Moscow region are generally more modernized than Krasnodar Krai. Since the mid-1980s, Moscow has been at the forefront of implementing policies of globalization, modernization, and informatization. This urban transformation has created a diverse cultural environment, where both European, liberal cultural norms and more conservative views coexist. At the mass level, multicultural dialogue is promoted, and the assimilation of new cultural norms is widespread among Moscow's population (Tishkov 2017). Krasnodar Krai, on the other hand, is often regarded as more traditional (Mukha 2012).

In summary, both Krasnodar Krai and Moscow region are economically developed areas of Russia, characterized by high-income levels and well-developed recreational infrastructures. However, Krasnodar Krai benefits from a warmer climate and is less urbanized and more traditional compared to Moscow region.

Having reviewed the socio-cultural context of both regions, as well as the findings of previous studies, it is clear that a cross-regional analysis of the role of values in psychological well-being in these regions is both timely and relevant.

In this study, we have formulated the following hypotheses and research questions:

Hypothesis 1. Residents of Krasnodar Krai exhibit higher levels of psychological well-being compared to residents of Moscow region.

Hypothesis 2. Residents of the more modernized Moscow region are more likely to emphasize values of personal focus (such as Openness to change and Self-Enhancement), whereas residents of the more traditional Krasnodar Krai prioritize values of social focus (such as Conservation and Self-Transcendence).

Hypothesis 3. The smallest differences between residents of Krasnodar Krai and Moscow region are found in the expression of values with medium and low significance, while the greatest differences are observed in values of high significance.

Research Question 1. What values determine the psychological well-being of residents in Moscow region and Krasnodar Krai?

Research Question 2. What universal and regionally specific patterns emerge in the relationship between values and psychological well-being?

To test these hypotheses and answer the research questions, we first analyzed data from a sample of residents in Moscow region, followed by an analysis of data from Krasnodar Krai. The results of these two samples were then compared to identify both commonalities and regional distinctions.

Research methodology

Procedure

The study was conducted online between 2021 and 2022 using the platform anketolog.ru. Participants were provided with a small reward for their participation. Previous studies have indicated that various socio-demographic factors – such as gender (Nupur and Mahapatro 2016), age (Frijters and Beaton 2012; Rodionova 2015), education (Bleidorn et al. 2016), income (Doroshenko 2019; Oishi and Kesebir 2015), and ethnic status (Arpino and de Valk 2017; Safi 2010; Gokdemir and Dumludag 2011) – can influence psychological well-being. Therefore, these variables were controlled in our analysis.

Research Sample

The initial sample from Moscow region (Moscow and Moscow Oblast) included 351 respondents. After applying the inclusion criteria (Russian ethnic group), the final sample for analysis consisted of 318 participants. The sample's age range was 18 to 70 years ($M = 39.6$; $SD = 11.92$). The gender distribution showed that 33.6% were men. In terms of education, 72.1% had higher education, 17.8% had specialized secondary education, 6.7% had secondary education, 0.6% had incomplete secondary education, and 2.9% held an academic degree. Regarding financial well-being, 15.9% reported living without financial difficulties, 51.6% found their income generally sufficient, 26.1% struggled to make ends meet, 8.5% faced significant financial challenges, and 0.9% found it difficult to answer.

The initial sample from Krasnodar Krai consisted of 468 respondents. After applying the same ethnic group inclusion criterion, the final sample for analysis was reduced to 407 participants. The sample's age range was 18 to 70 years ($M = 31.9$; $SD = 13.75$). Men accounted for 33.6% of respondents. As for education, 58.6% held higher education, 10.2% had sec-

ondary specialized education, 23.1% had secondary education, 6.1% had incomplete secondary education, and 2% had academic degrees. Financially, 15.9% reported living without financial difficulties, 45.4% found their income generally sufficient, 25.2% struggled to meet basic expenses, 7.7% experienced significant financial hardship, and 5.7% found it difficult to answer.

Measures

Individual values. The Schwartz Value Survey (SVS) was used for European Social Research (Magun and Rudnev 2008). It includes 21 statements that measure the expression of 10 values: Independence, Stimulation, Hedonism, Achievement, Power, Security, Tradition, Conformity, Universalism, and Benevolence. These values are then combined into higher-order categories: Openness to change, Self-Enhancement, Conservation, and Self-Transcendence. An example of a statement: “It is important for him to come up with new things and approach everything creatively. He likes to do everything in his own way, in his own original way” (this corresponds to the value of Self-direction, within the Openness to change category).

Psychological well-being was measured by two constructs: self-esteem and life satisfaction.

Self-esteem (Rosenberg 1965). A translated and adapted scale was used, consisting of 4 statements. For example: “Overall, I’m happy with myself.”

Life satisfaction (Diener et al. 1985). The Life Satisfaction Scale, translated into Russian and adapted for the study, was used. It includes 4 statements, for example: “In most cases, my life is close to ideal.”

Mathematical and statistical processing of the results included descriptive statistics, analysis of variance (ANOVA), Cronbach’s alpha (for reliability), and regression analysis (hierarchical regression).

Results of the study

An interregional analysis of the severity of individual values and indicators of psychological well-being among Russians in Krasnodar Krai and Moscow region using ANOVA showed significant interregional differences: Wilks’s $\Lambda = 0.837$, $F(11.713) = 16.234$, $p = 0.000$, $\eta^2 = 0.163$ (see Table 1).

The results show that both self-esteem and life satisfaction are significantly higher among residents of Krasnodar Krai compared to those in Moscow region. This suggests that psychological well-being is more typical for residents of Krasnodar Krai, confirming our first hypothesis.

When analyzing values, it can be noted that the values of Self-direction (from the Openness to change block), Security, and Conformity (from the Conservation block) are more pronounced among residents of Moscow region compared to Krasnodar Krai. In contrast, the values of Stimulation, Hedonism (from the Openness to change block), Achievement (from the Self-Enhancement block), and Benevolence (from the Self-Transcendence block) hold greater importance for residents of Krasnodar Krai. The values of Power, Tradition, and Universalism did not show significant differences in their average scores. These findings suggest that the importance of these values is similar for residents of both regions, partially confirming our second hypothesis.

Table 1. Comparison of the severity of values and indicators of psychological well-being among Russians in Moscow region and Krasnodar Krai

Variables	Moscow region		Krasnodar Krai		F(3. 722)	Partial η^2
	M(SD)	α	M(SD)	α		
	Values					
Self-direction	4.33 (0.84)	0.66	4.23 (0.80)	0.69	3.404†	0.004
Stimulation	3.40 (0.98)	0.65	3.63 (0.99)	0.67	9.780**	0.010
Hedonism	3.83 (0.91)	0.69	4.05 (0.94)	0.71	11.516***	0.012
Achievement	3.88 (0.89)	0.70	4.08 (0.86)	0.70	11.209***	0.012
Power	3.63 (0.90)	0.67	3.60 (0.90)	0.66	0.887	0.001
Security	4.75 (0.78)	0.69	4.34 (0.91)	0.68	42.746***	0.044
Tradition	3.73 (1.04)	0.56	3.68 (1.08)	0.57	0.268	0.000
Conformity	3.59 (0.88)	0.69	3.47 (0.89)	0.68	3.656*	0.004
Universalism	4.44 (0.62)	0.67	4.42 (0.67)	0.69	0.325	0.000
Benevolence	4.26 (0.80)	0.70	4.40 (0.76)	0.71	7.046**	0.008
	Psychological well-being research					
Self-esteem	3.34 (0.99)	0.88	3.94 (0.80)	0.90	93.494***	0.092
Life satisfaction	2.87 (0.83)	0.87	3.28 (0.87)	0.88	48.164***	0.049

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, † $p = 0.06$.

The results also show partial confirmation of our third hypothesis: values such as Power and Tradition were the least significant, with a consensus on their relative importance in both regions. Conversely, values like Self-direction, Security, and Benevolence were highly significant for the respondents, showing notable interregional differences. Additionally, significant differences were observed in values ranked as low and medium in the hierarchy, such as Stimulation, Hedonism, Achievement, and Conformity. However, there was a consensus on the value of Universalism, which was highly important to Russians in both regions.

To answer our first and second research questions, we performed a regression analysis. Hierarchical regression was used, with socio-demographic characteristics tested in the first step, followed by the values from the Openness to change block, the Self-Enhancement block, the Conservation block, and, in the final step, the Self-Transcendence block. Table 2 presents the data for Moscow region.

The results showed that in the Openness to change block, only the value of Self-direction was positively associated with the self-esteem of Russians in Moscow region. This suggests that the more important independence of thought and action, as well as a creative approach, is to respondents, the higher their level of self-esteem. Additionally, the value of Benevolence was positively correlated with life satisfaction: the more meaningful it is for respondents to maintain a benevolent attitude toward others, the more satisfied they are with life.

The values in the Self-Enhancement block did not show significant correlations with either self-esteem or life satisfaction among Russians in Moscow region.

In the Conservation block, the value of Conformity was positively related to life satisfaction, while Tradition was positively related to both self-esteem and life satisfaction. This

indicates that the more respondents value observing rules and maintaining order, the more satisfied they are with life. Moreover, the more Russians in Moscow region are focused on preserving cultural traditions and customs, particularly within the family, the higher their psychological well-being (both self-esteem and life satisfaction).

The analysis of socio-demographic indicators revealed a positive effect of subjective income level on the psychological well-being of Russians in Moscow region: the higher respondents' income, the more satisfied they are with life and the higher their self-esteem.

Table 2. The relationship of self-esteem and life satisfaction with the individual values of Russians in Moscow region

Independent variables	Dependent variables				
	Indicators of psychological well-being: self-esteem/life satisfaction				
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Socio-demographic variables					
Age	0.07 / 0.05	0.07 / 0.08	0.07 / 0.07	0.02 / 0.02	0.02 / 0.03
Gender (male – 1, female – 2)	-0.00 / 0.05	0.00 / 0.04	-0.00 / 0.04	-0.01 / 0.03	-0.01 / 0.03
Education level	-0.04 / 0.05	-0.06 / 0.04	-0.07 / 0.05	-0.06 / 0.06	-0.05 / 0.05
Income	0.23*** / 0.31***	0.23*** / 0.31***	0.23*** / 0.31***	0.22*** / 0.30***	0.22*** / 0.31***
Values of Openness to change					
Self-direction		0.14* / 0.04	0.14* / 0.05	0.12* / 0.09	0.15* / 0.07
Stimulation		0.01 / 0.07	-0.00 / 0.07	0.00 / 0.04	0.01 / 0.02
Hedonism		-0.02 / 0.04	-0.04 / 0.06	-0.05 / 0.06	-0.04 / 0.05
Self-Enhancement Values					
Achievement			0.06 / -0.02	0.04 / -0.02	0.06 / -0.06
Power			-0.03 / -0.03	-0.02 / -0.02	-0.03 / 0.01
Conservation Values					
Security				0.08 / -0.08	0.10 / -0.10
Conformity				0.03 / 0.14*	0.04 / 0.12*
Tradition				0.18** / 0.23***	0.21** / 0.17**
Values of Self-Transcendence					
Benevolence					-0.04 / 0.20***
Universalism					-0.09 / -0.09
R ²	0.053 / 0.102	0.072 / 0.114	0.074 / 0.115	0.123 / 0.199	0.130 / 0.226
ΔR ²	0.053 / 0.102	0.019 / 0.012	0.002 / 0.001	0.049 / 0.084	0.008 / 0.028
F	4.38** / 8.79***	3.40** / 5.63***	2.70** / 4.41***	3.52*** / 6.25***	3.21*** / 6.27***

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Next, we analyzed the relationship between values and well-being indicators among residents of Krasnodar Krai. Hierarchical regression was also applied, with the results presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Relationship of self-esteem and life satisfaction with the individual values of Russians in Krasnodar Krai

Independent variables	Dependent variables				
	Indicators of psychological well-being: self-esteem/life satisfaction				
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Socio-demographic variables					
Age	-0.13** / 0.01	-0.06 / 0.02	-0.05 / 0.02	-0.07 / -0.02	-0.07 / -0.01
Gender (male - 1, female - 2)	0.16*** / 0.16***	0.13** / 0.15***	0.15** / 0.15**	0.12* / 0.14**	0.11* / 0.14**
Education level	0.16*** / -0.01	0.12* / -0.03	0.10* / -0.03	0.07 / -0.02	0.06 / -0.02
Income	0.04 / 0.29***	0.03 / 0.29***	0.05 / 0.29***	0.05 / 0.30***	0.06 / 0.30***
Values of Openness to change					
Self-direction		0.20*** / 0.06	0.17*** / 0.07	0.16** / 0.06	0.15** / 0.07
Stimulation		0.05 / 0.04	0.02 / 0.02	0.04 / 0.03	0.04 / 0.03
Hedonism		0.12* / 0.01	0.06 / 0.01	0.05 / -0.01	0.04 / -0.02
Self-Enhancement Values					
Achievement			0.11 / 0.10	0.07 / 0.12*	0.06 / 0.12*
Power			0.08 / -0.04	0.07 / -0.02	0.08 / -0.02
Conservation Values					
Security				0.13* / -0.10	0.12* / -0.10
Tradition				0.08 / 0.28***	0.05 / 0.27***
Conformity				-0.01 / -0.01	-0.06 / -0.01
Values of Self-Transcendence					
Benevolence					0.03 / 0.02
Universalism					0.12* / -0.01
R ²	0.063 / 0.034	0.207 / 0.081	0.217 / 0.082	0.232 / 0.143	0.240 / 0.145
ΔR ²	0.063 / 0.034	0.144 / 0.047	0.010 / 0.002	0.015 / 0.060	0.008 / 0.002
F	10.09*** / 5.28***	22.45*** / 7.54***	18.50*** / 5.98***	15.04*** / 8.28***	13.45*** / 7.21***

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

The results regarding the values in the Openness to change block showed that the value of Independence is positively correlated with self-esteem. The value of Hedonism was positively associated with self-esteem only at the second step of the analysis, after which the effect was no longer significant. This suggests that when respondents value self-direction

of thought and action, as well as pleasure, they tend to have a higher level of self-esteem. Additionally, the values of Universalism were positively related to self-esteem: the more important tolerance and acceptance of others are to respondents, the higher their self-esteem.

Achievement values were positively correlated with life satisfaction. This indicates that when Russians in Krasnodar Krai value success and achievement, they experience greater life satisfaction.

The values of Security were positively correlated with self-esteem, while the values of Tradition were positively correlated with life satisfaction. This suggests that the more respondents value their own security and the security of their loved ones, the higher their self-esteem. Likewise, the more important it is for respondents to preserve traditions and customs, the higher their life satisfaction.

Regarding socio-demographic characteristics, it was found that psychological well-being (both self-esteem and life satisfaction) is higher among women than men, and people with higher education tend to have higher self-esteem. Additionally, respondents with higher subjective income levels reported greater life satisfaction.

A comparative interregional analysis revealed that in both regions, the values of Self-direction predict a high level of self-esteem, and the values of Tradition predict higher life satisfaction. This represents a universal pattern across both regions.

When examining regional differences, it was found that the value of Security (from the Conservation block) is more significant for life satisfaction among Russians in Krasnodar Krai, while the value of Conformity (also from the Conservation block) is more significant for life satisfaction among Russians in Moscow region.

In the Self-Transcendence block, Benevolence is more important for life satisfaction in Moscow region, while Universalism is positively correlated with self-esteem among residents of Krasnodar Krai.

Finally, while the values in the Self-Enhancement block did not predict psychological well-being in Moscow region, the Achievement value from this block was significant for life satisfaction among residents of Krasnodar Krai.

Discussion of results and conclusions

Our research aimed to analyze the role of values in the psychological well-being of residents in two regions of Russia (the Moscow region and Krasnodar Krai). We focused on identifying similarities and differences between these regions.

The data showed that psychological well-being is more pronounced among residents of Krasnodar Krai compared to those in the Moscow region. Given that macro indicators such as income and GDP are more favorable in the Moscow region, it can be concluded that these factors do not determine Russians' well-being at an individual level. Other researchers have obtained similar results when studying the relationship between macro indicators (GDP level, average income level) and psychological well-being in Russia (Salnikova 2019). Their study found that macroeconomic factors do not directly influence people's assessment of their well-being.

Our data highlight the significant impact of climatic conditions on well-being indicators. It can be assumed that the more favorable climate of Krasnodar Krai contributes to the significantly higher level of psychological well-being in this region compared to the Moscow

region. These findings are supported by research on the relationship between climate and subjective well-being across Russian regions (Kovalev et al. 2017).

It cannot be stated unequivocally that socially oriented values are more pronounced among residents of a more traditional region (Krasnodar Krai), while personally oriented values are more characteristic of residents of a more modernized region (Moscow). Although previous studies have confirmed this pattern (Magun and Rudnev 2010), our findings suggest that the expression of certain values may not be directly linked to the level of modernization or tradition in a region.

In our view, the prominence of certain values may be influenced by cultural diversity, the complexity of the social structure, and the specifics of economic activity. For example, in the Moscow region, which has a more complex social structure, greater heterogeneity in development levels, and a large number of non-local migrants, independence is crucial for individual self-realization. At the same time, maintaining common rules and ensuring a sense of security for all remain important. Consequently, the values of Self-direction, Security, and Conformity hold greater significance for residents of the Moscow region.

In contrast, Krasnodar Krai, which is oriented towards the development of the recreational industry, fosters values associated with risk-taking, stimulation, hedonism, and the pursuit of success. At the same time, maintaining a friendly attitude towards visitors and tourists is essential. Therefore, the values of Stimulation, Hedonism, Achievement, and Benevolence are more pronounced among residents of Krasnodar Krai compared to those in the Moscow region. However, these assumptions require further verification in other regions.

Our data also showed that values of low importance to Russian respondents – namely Power and Tradition – exhibited no regional differences. This finding is consistent with previous studies (Fischer and Schwartz 2011), which suggest that value consensus within a country is often reflected in the least significant values. Interestingly, the highly significant value of Universalism also showed no regional differences. This may be due to its declining importance in Russia (Magun 2023), leading to a relatively high level of interregional consensus regarding this value.

Other values of high importance – Self-direction, Security, and Benevolence – showed significant interregional differences, which is consistent with previous studies (Fischer and Schwartz 2011). However, the values of Stimulation, Hedonism, Achievement, and Conformity, which were of low to moderate importance, also differed between the two regions.

Our research revealed that the self-esteem of Russians living in the Moscow region is primarily determined by the value of Self-direction (part of the Openness to change value block, associated with personal focus). Life satisfaction increases with the growing importance of Conformity (part of the Conservation value block, associated with social focus) and Benevolence (part of the Self-Transcendence value block, also associated with social focus). Additionally, the value of Tradition (within the Conservation block) has a positive effect on both self-esteem and life satisfaction among residents of Moscow region.

Our findings align with previous research showing that the values of Openness to change and Self-Transcendence contribute to psychological well-being (Sortheix and Schwartz 2017). Moreover, a study conducted in Russia found that values associated with moral excellence are positively linked to psychological well-being (Balabanova 2023). However, our data on the relationship between psychological well-being and the values of the Conservation block (Conformity and Tradition) diverge from previous studies (Sortheix and Schwartz

2017). In Schwartz's (2012) value model, Conformity and Tradition are classified as values aimed at anxiety avoidance, which, under normal conditions, tend to have a neutral or negative impact on psychological well-being. However, our study, conducted in 2021–2022, took place in a context of heightened anxiety and external threats. In such a situation, the values of Conformity and Tradition, which emphasize maintaining order, adhering to norms and rules, and preserving traditions and customs, may help individuals cope with fear, thereby contributing to psychological well-being. It is possible that these values also reflect the importance of identification with a social group, national satisfaction, and national pride, which, in turn, enhance the psychological well-being of Russians (Kamalov and Ponarin 2020).

The results obtained from the Krasnodar Krai sample showed that Russians' self-esteem is determined by the values of Self-direction, Hedonism, Security, and Universalism. Life satisfaction among Russians in Krasnodar Krai depends on the significance of Achievement and Tradition – the more important these values are, the higher the level of life satisfaction. Our findings partially align with previous studies (Sagiv and Schwartz 2000; Bojanowska and Czerw 2020; Bobowik et al. 2011), particularly in relation to the values of Self-direction, Hedonism, and Universalism. However, similar to the Moscow region, the psychological well-being of Russians in Krasnodar Krai is also influenced by the values of the Conservation block (Security and Tradition).

It can be assumed that values focused on self-protection and anxiety avoidance – namely Security and Tradition – play a key role in predicting psychological well-being in situations of increased external threats. Additionally, these values may reflect the importance of national pride and national satisfaction, which, in turn, contribute to higher subjective well-being among Russians (Kamalov and Ponarin 2020).

Unlike previous studies, which provide no clear data on the role of Achievement values, our findings suggest that this value contributes to life satisfaction among Russians in Krasnodar Krai. Similar conclusions were drawn by Balabanova (2023), who examined the relationship between values and well-being among specialists in Russian business organizations, finding that Achievement values are positively associated with both economic and psychological well-being.

Regarding the role of socio-demographic characteristics, our research revealed that a key factor in both regions is the subjective level of income. These results are consistent with findings from Russian samples (Gurko 2023) and international studies (Smoleva 2020). We also identified regional differences: in Krasnodar Krai, women report higher psychological well-being than men, which is consistent with earlier findings in Russia (Shaekhov 2021). Besides, in Krasnodar Krai, individuals with a higher level of education exhibit higher self-esteem, which aligns with previous studies (Balabanova 2023; Nupur and Mahapatro 2016).

Continuing the analysis of cross-regional similarities and differences, we note that the value of Self-direction is positively associated with self-esteem, while the value of Tradition is linked to life satisfaction among Russians in both regions. This relationship appears to be universal. Previous studies (Sortheix and Schwartz 2017) have demonstrated a positive relationship between Self-direction and psychological well-being. However, findings on the relationship between Tradition and well-being have been inconsistent. We can assume that, in this case, the relevance of specific values to a given culture plays a more significant role in determining well-being (Friedlmeier et al. 2008). Perhaps, under the current conditions of external challenges and threats, preserving cultural traditions and customs has become

increasingly important for Russians, making this value a key factor in life satisfaction in both regions.

The values within the Self-Transcendence block also serve as predictors of psychological well-being, but their impact differs by region: in Moscow region, the key predictor is Benevolence, while in Krasnodar Krai, the key predictor is Universalism.

This distinction may be explained by historical and cultural factors. Krasnodar Krai, as a historically multicultural region, places significant importance on universal and equal treatment of different social groups, which could explain why Universalism is associated with life satisfaction in this region. In contrast, in Moscow region, where individuals tend to have a higher degree of autonomy and independence, a value related to care and mutual assistance – Benevolence – plays a more significant role in shaping self-esteem and self-respect.

In terms of cross-regional differences, it can be noted that the value of Security is more significant for self-esteem among Russians in Krasnodar Krai, whereas the value of Conformity plays a greater role in life satisfaction among Russians in Moscow Region. Although both values are focused on self-protection and anxiety avoidance, their specific meanings and significance differ. This distinction may be influenced by territorial and geographical factors: Moscow Region is geographically vast and highly heterogeneous. In such an environment, maintaining order and adhering to common norms and rules may be crucial for stability and social cohesion. This could explain why Conformity plays a key role in the well-being of its residents. Krasnodar Krai, as a border region with a high influx of forced and labor migrants, may place greater importance on Security as a means of ensuring stability and well-being.

Additionally, in Krasnodar Krai, we identified a significant positive effect of the Achievement value on life satisfaction. In a relatively traditional region, where public opinion holds considerable weight, a person's successes and accomplishments may serve as important indicators of their well-being, contributing to higher life satisfaction. Notably, we did not observe a similar effect in Moscow region.

Summing up, we can conclude that Russians in Krasnodar Krai exhibit significantly higher psychological well-being compared to those in Moscow Region. Moscow Region residents place greater emphasis on the values of Self-direction, Security, and Conformity, while Krasnodar Krai residents prioritize Stimulation, Hedonism, Achievement, and Benevolence. The values of Power, Tradition, and Universalism show no significant regional differences.

The positive relationship between Self-direction and self-esteem as well as Tradition and life satisfaction in both regions can be considered universal. However, cultural and regional specificity is reflected in other value-well-being relationships: in Moscow Region, well-being is associated with the values of Benevolence and Conformity and in Krasnodar Krai, well-being is linked to Universalism, Security, and Achievement.

These findings broaden the applicability of value theory in explaining psychological well-being in the face of external threats. Our data suggest that, in situations of danger and external challenges, values focused on self-protection and anxiety avoidance – such as Tradition, Conformity, and Security – become key predictors of psychological well-being in Russian regions. Furthermore, the study underscores the importance of regional factors in understanding the value-based determinants of psychological well-being. These insights can be valuable for shaping social and regional policies.

This study has certain limitations, primarily due to the nature of online surveys, which may influence response patterns. Additionally, the results require further verification in other Russian regions to ensure broader applicability.

Reference list

- Apatova NV, Avdeeva KV (2016) The impact of recreational infrastructure on the development of the region. *International Scientific Research Journal* 9(51): 13-15. doi: 10.18454/IRJ.2016.51.094.
- Arutyunova EM (2014) Socio-political orientations and interethnic harmony. In: Drobizheva LM (Ed) *Resource of interethnic harmony in Moscow*. Moscow: Institute of Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 44-53.
- Balabanova ES (2023) Values and resources as factors of social well-being of specialists of Russian business organizations. *Russian World* 32(1): 6-36. <https://doi.org/10.17323/1811-038X-2023-32-1-6-36>.
- Baranov AV, Skorobogatov VV (2019) Ethnopolitical relations and their regulation in the border regions of Russia (on the example of Krasnodar Krai). *Society: Politics, Economics, Law* 9(74): 15-20. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336387958_Etnopoliticeskie_otnosenia_i_ih_regulirovanie_v_prigranicnyh_regionah_rossi_na_primere_krasnodarskog_kraa.
- Batchaev A (2022) Russian ratings of regions recommended for use in strategic planning. URL: <https://stratplan.ru/UserFiles/Files/Russian%20regions.pdf> (accessed on 19.02.2023).
- Vnukova LB (2020) Interrelation of values and ideological preferences in the minds of students in the South of Russia (based on the materials of a sociological study). *National security/nota bene* (5): 56-72. https://nbpublish.com/library_read_article.php?id=34272 (accessed on 19.10.2021).
- Gurko TA (2023) Dynamics of vital activity and factors of adolescent well-being. *Mir Rossii* 32(4): 119-137. <https://doi.org/10.17323/1811-038X-2023-32-4-119-137>.
- Doroshenko EV (2019) The level of well-being: the relationship between income and personal characteristics of a person. *The Manager* 10(1): 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.29141/2218-5003-2019-10-1-6>.
- Efremova KA (2017) From regionalism to transregionalism: a theoretical understanding of the new reality. *Comparative Politics* (2): 58-72. doi: 10.18611/2221-3279-2017-8-2-58-72.
- Kamalov EA, Ponarin ED (2020) National pride and the subjective well-being of Russians. *Public Opinion Monitoring: Economic and Social Changes* (1): 177-205. <https://doi.org/10.14515/monitoring.2020.1.08>.
- Kovalev SY, Blam I, Mkrtchyan GM, Tselodub YuO (2017) Climate impact on subjective assessments of household welfare in Russia. *Region: Economics and Sociology* (3): 254-276. <https://doi.org/10.15372/REG20170313>.
- Korobitsyn BA (2015) Methodological approach to accounting for the depletion of natural resources, changes in the state of the environment and human capital in the gross regional product. *Economy of the region* (3): 77-88.
- Kuznetsov DA (2016) The phenomenon of transregionalism: problems of terminology and conceptualization. *Comparative Politics* 7(23): 14-25. doi: 10.18611/2221-3279-2016-7-2(23)-14-25.
- Kulikov LV (2000) *Determinants of life satisfaction. Society and politics*. St. Petersburg: Publishing House of St. Petersburg University, 476-510 pp.
- Lagutina ML, Mikhailenko EB (2020) Regionalism in the Global Era: a review of foreign and Russian approaches. *Bulletin of the Peoples' Friendship University of Russia. Series: International Relations* 20(2): 261-278. <https://doi.org/10.22363/2313-0660-2020-20-2-261-278>.
- Leonidova GV, Ustinova KA, Gordievskaya AN (2017) A study of the values of the population with traditional and modern views. *Problems of territorial development* 5(91): 41-58.
- Lepshokova ZH, Vylegzhanina MS (2017) The role of individual values of representatives of the host population in their acculturation expectations. *Cultural and Historical Psychology* 13(4): 40-48.

- Magun V, Rudnev M (2008) Vital values of the Russian population: similarities and differences in comparison with other European countries. *Bulletin of Public Opinion. Data. Analysis. Discussions* (1): 33-58.
- Magun V, Rudnev M (2010) International comparisons of the basic values of the Russian population and the dynamics of socialization processes. *Educational Policy* 7-8: 45-46.
- Magun VS The evolution of the basic values of the Russian population, 2006-2021 (2023) // *Sociological Research* (12): 44-59. doi: 10.31857/S013216250029336-2.
- Malkina MY (2016) Evaluation of the social well-being of Russian regions, the level and dynamics of inter-regional disparities based on welfare functions. *TERRA ECONOMICUS* 14(3): 29-49. <https://doi.org/10.18522/2073-6606-2016-14-3-29-49>.
- Malkina MY (2017) Social well-being of the regions of the Russian Federation. *Economics of the region* 13(1): 49-62. doi: 10.17059/2017-1-5.
- Mukha VN (2012) The ethnosocial and ethnocultural environment of Krasnodar Krai. URL: https://superinf.ru/view_helpstud.php?id=1899 (accessed on 10.10.2021).
- The regions of Russia with the most psychologically healthy inhabitants are named (2021) News.ru, January 16. URL: https://finance.rambler.ru/economics/45619448/?utm_content=finance-media&utm_medium=read_more&utm_source=copylink (accessed on 12.10.2023).
- Nartova-Bochaver SK (2005) *The psychological space of personality: a monograph*. Moscow: Prometheus, 312 pp.
- Population of Russian regions in 2023: number, large regions of Russia and federal districts (list, table) (2023) URL: https://www.statdata.ru/largest_regions_russia (accessed on 11.12.2023).
- National composition of the regions of Russia (2023) URL: <https://www.statdata.ru/nacionalnyj-sostav-oblastei-rossii> (accessed on 11.12.2023).
- National Tourism Rating 2023 (2024) URL: https://rustur.ru/nacionalnyj-turisticheskij-rejting-2023?roistat_visit=1375347 (accessed on 19.03.2024).
- Pyzhev AI, Pyzheva Yul (2015) Assessment of the regional socio-ecological and economic well-being of Krasnoyarsk Krai: a new approach. *Regional economics: theory and practice* 34(409): 30-40.
- Rodionova LA (2015) Age-related features of a happy life in Russia and Europe: an econometric approach. *Applied Econometrics* 40(4): 64-83.
- Smoleva EO (2020) Happiness and money: material aspects of subjective well-being. *Problems of territorial development* 3(107): 144-166. doi: 10.15838/ptd.2020.3.107.10.
- Tishkov VA (2017) The world experience of polyethnicity and Russia: three reasons for interest. In: VA Tishkov, VV Stepanov (Eds) *Ethnic and religious diversity of Russia*. Moscow: IEA RAS, 11-21 pp.
- The level of urbanization by regions of Russia in 2022 (2022) URL: <https://xn--80apggvco.xn--p1ai/%D0%BA%D0%B0%D1%80%D1%82%D1%8B?id=208> (accessed on 11.12.2023).
- Shaekhov ZD (2021) Psychological well-being in the context of gender and sexual identity. *National Psychological Journal* 3 (43): 31-42. doi: 10.11621/npj.2021.0303.
- Shamionov RM (2014) Group values and attitudes as predictors of psychological well-being of Russians and Kazakhs. *Psychological Research* 7(35). <http://www.psystudy.ru/index.php/num/2014v7n35/999-shamionov35.html> (accessed on 16.02.2023).
- Shamionov RM (2010) On some transformations of the structure of the subjective well-being of the individual in different conditions of professional socialization. *World of Psychology* (1): 237-249.
- Acharya A (2012) Comparative Regionalism: A Field Whose Time has Come? *The International Spectator: Italian Journal of International Affairs* 47(1): 3-15.
- Arpino B, de Valk H (2017) Comparing Life Satisfaction of Immigrants and Natives Across Europe: The Role of Social Contacts. *Soc Indic Res Springer*. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007%2Fs11205-017-1629-x.pdf> (accessed on 20.11.23).

- Bilsky W, Schwartz SH (1994) Values and personality. *European Journal of Personality* 8: 163-181.
- Bleidorn W, Arslan RC, Denissen JJA, Rentfrow PJ, Gebauer JE, Potter J, Gosling SD (2016) Age and Gender differences in self-esteem-A cross-cultural Window. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 111(3): 396–410.
- Bobowik M, Basabe N, Paez D, Jimenez A, Bilbao MA (2011) Personal values and well-being among Europeans, Spanish natives and immigrants to Spain: Does the culture matter? *Journal of Happiness Studies* 1(12): 401-419. doi: 10.1007/s10902-010-9202-1.
- Bojanowska A, Czerw A (2020) Values and well-being – how are individual values associated with subjective and eudaimonic well-being? *Polish Psychological Bulletin* 51(2): 162-169. doi: 10.24425/ppb.2020.133773.
- Diener E, Emmons RA, Larsen RJ, Griffin S (1985) The Satisfaction with Life Scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment* 49: 1-5. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa4901_13.
- Diener E, Sapryta JJ, Suh E (1998) Subjective well-being is essential to well-being. *Psychological Inquiry* 9: 33-37.
- Fischer R, Schwartz S (2011) Whence Differences in Value Priorities? Individual, Cultural, or Artfactual Sources. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 42(7): 1127–1144. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00220221110381429>.
- Friedlmeier W, Schäfermeier E, Vasconcellos V, Trommsdorff G (2008) Self-construal and cultural orientation as predictors for developmental goals: A comparison between Brazilian and German caregivers. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology* 5: 39-67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405620600751085>.
- Frijters P, Beaton T (2012) The mystery of the U-shaped relationship between happiness and age. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization* 82: 525-542.
- Galyapina VN, Lebedeva N, Lepshokova Z, Boehnke K (2018) Values of Ethnic Russian Minority Members in North Caucasus Republics of the Russian Federation: An Inter- and Intragenerational Comparison. In: Lebedeva N, Dimitrova R, Berry JW (Eds) *Changing Values and Identities in Post-Communist World*. Switzerland: Springer, Ch. 8, 157-173 pp. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72616-8_9.
- Germani A, Delvecchio E, Li J-B, Lis A, Nartova-Bochaver SK, Vazsonyi AT, Mazzeschi C (2021) The link between individualism–collectivism and life satisfaction among emerging adults from four countries. *International Association of Applied Psychology* 13(2): 437-453. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aphw.12259>.
- Gokdemir O, Dumludag D (2011) Subjective well-being among ethnic minorities: the Dutch case Munich Personal RePEc Archive MPRA.
- Grosz MP, Schwartz SH, Lechner C (2021) Values & Well Being Longitudinal Supplement December 2020. *European Journal of Personality* (in press).
- Inglehart R, Welzel C (2003) Political Culture and Democracy: Analyzing the Cross Level Linkages. *Comparative Politics* 36: 61–79.
- Laursen F (2003) *Comparative Regional Integration: Theoretical Perspectives*. Ashgate.
- Lyubomirsky S, King L, Diener E (2005) The Benefits of Frequent Positive Affect: Does Happiness Lead to Success? *Psychological Bulletin* Copyright 131(6): 803– 855.
- Minkov M, Sokolov B, Ponarin E, Almakaeva A, Nastina E (2023) Is “Regional Culture” a Meaningful Concept? Cultural Differences Across 60 Russian Regions. *Cross Cultural and Strategic Management* 30 (3): 637-656. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CCSM-07-2022-0126>.
- Nupur C, Mahapatro M (2016) Gender Differences in Self Esteem among Young Adults of Raipur, Uttar Pradesh, India. *Austin J Womens Health* 3(1):1018-1022.
- Oishi S, Kesebir S (2015) Income inequality explains why economic growth does not always translate to an increase in happiness. *Psychological Science* 26 (10): 1630–1638.

- Orth U, Robins RW (2014) The development of self-esteem. *Current Directions in Psychological Science* 23: 381–387.
- Rosenberg M (1965) Society and the Adolescent Self-Image. *Social Forces* 44 (2): 255-256. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/44.2.255>.
- Ryff CD (1989) Happiness is Everything, or Is It? Explorations on the Meaning of Psychological Well-Being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 57(6): 1069–1081.
- Safi M (2010) Immigrants' life satisfaction in Europe: Between assimilation and discrimination. *European Sociological Review* 26: 159–176.
- Sagiv L, Schwartz SH (2000) Value priorities and subjective well-being: Direct relations and congruence effects. *European Journal of Social Psychology* 30: 177-198.
- Salnikova D (2019) Factors of subjective household economic well-being in transition countries: Friends or institutions in need? *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy* 39(9-10): 695-718.
- Schwartz SH (1992) Universals in the content and structure of values: Theoretical advances and empirical tests in 20 countries. In: Zanna MP (Ed) *Advances in experimental social psychology*. New York: Academic Press 25: 1–65.
- Schwartz S (2012) *Toward Refining the Theory of Basic Human Values in: Methods, Theories, and Empirical Applications in the Social Sciences*. Wiesbaden: Springer.
- Schwartz SH (2012a) An Overview of the Schwartz Theory of Basic Values. *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture* 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1116>.
- Sortheix FM, Schwartz S (2017) Values that Underlie and Undermine Well-Being: Variability across Countries. *European Journal of Personality* 31(2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/per.2096>.
- Stones MJ, Kozma A (1985) Structural relationships among happiness scales: A second order factorial study. *Social Indicators Research* 17: 19-28.

Information about the author

- Victoria Nikolaevna Galyapina – Doctor of Psychology, Assistant Professor, Professor of School of Psychology, Chief Researcher of Center for Sociocultural Research. Faculty of Social Sciences, National Research University Higher School of Economics. Moscow, 101000, Russia. E-mail: vgalyapina@hse.ru
- Zarina Khizirovna Lepshokova – Candidate of Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor of School of Psychology, Chief Researcher of Center for Sociocultural Research. Faculty of Social Sciences, National Research University Higher School of Economics. Moscow, 101000, Russia. E-mail: zlepshokova@hse.ru
- Ivan Aleksandrovich Apollonov – Doctor of Philosophy, Assistant Professor, Professor of Department of History, Philosophy and Psychology. Kuban State Technological University. Krasnodar, 350072, Russia. E-mail: obligo@yandex.ru